

THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the willingness and ability to solve problems, navigate the limitless flow of information, find the right answers from the alternatives offered by life, develop the human resources inherent in nature in working on the individuality of each individual, show true interest in what you love, be interested in the latest methodological advances in science, that will lay everything foundation of the education of the future.

Keywords: teacher, student, competence, approach, methodology, methodological category, foreign language education, technology.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization, education takes priority in the social sphere of a person. Education is an integral part of self-development, self-knowledge of a person, the key to a successful future, the well-being of the country and society. Domestic education has dynamically adapted to the changing conditions of the educational process, while occupying its niche in the world community. This predetermined the development of new approaches in education and science, the importance of which is highlighted in the works of major domestic and foreign scientists.

The final product of the educational process should be considered not knowledge, but competencies as such. It is the willingness and ability to solve problems, navigate the limitless flow of information, find the right answers from the alternatives offered by life, develop the human resources inherent in nature in working on the individuality of each individual, show true interest in what you love, be interested in the latest methodological advances in science, that will lay everything foundation of the education of the future. All this predetermined a change in the educational paradigm.

The new educational paradigm has created the need to create a new type of education, which is foreign language education, which meets all the requirements of the practice and theory of modern methodological science. A modern student shows

creative initiative in completing tasks, determines ways and methods for solving assigned problems, is an independent acquirer of knowledge, an expert, capable of critically analyzing information, passing it through the prism of his worldview and views. An important quality of today's student is to adequately monitor his professional development, analyze professional activities, which, through the efforts of teachers, are laid within the walls of the university.

Education is a purposeful, controlled, system-regulated process and standing in time, as it is a necessity and a need, reflecting the human essence in the desire for self-improvement and transformation of nature and the world around it.

Objectives of the article are:

1) To develop a model for the formation of professional communicative competence in the unity of linguistic-professional, pragmatic, discursive, strategic and communicative sub competences, to reveal its criterion-feature aspects, to develop a typology of exercises and to test it in the course of experimental work.

2) Justify the cognitive-reflexive-axiological approach as a conceptual basis that reflects the methodological basis of professional communicative communication.

3) Develop the structural composition of the professional communication module as a unit of subject content: select subject content to reflect basic courses, blocks and technologies.

4) To substantiate the didactic value of digital technologies as a single mechanism for the formation of professional and communicative competence in the conditions of digitalization of education.

The leading idea of the study

The formation of professional and communicative competence in the context of digitalization of foreign language education is characterized by a high degree of efficiency, since the latest digital technologies, supporting integration processes: cognition, reflection and axiology, provide effective organization of professional communication, formation of a linguistic and professional background, organization of the process of revealing language as a translator of professional communication, which is ultimately aimed at developing professional communicative competence in the subject of professional communication.

Scientific novelty

– the updated essence of “professional-communicative competence” as a goal-resulting methodological category of foreign language education has been revealed, and its component composition and criterion-feature aspects have been developed; – the cognitive-reflexive-axiological approach is substantiated as the conceptual basis of professional communicative communication, the educational product of which is the personality of the subject of professional communication, who owns the entire arsenal

of tactics and strategies of intercultural communication in the conditions of its digitalization;

– a professional communication module has been developed, consisting of an educational block, including: basic courses, modules and technologies;

– a new component composition of the content of foreign language education in the context of digitalization has been determined;

– the didactic value of the latest digital technologies has been proven, regulating the interdependent process of formation and development of the personality of the subject of professional communication in the conditions of digitalization.

The practical significance of digital technologies

The practical significance of the study lies in the development of a methodology for the gradual formation of professional communicative competence, consisting of professionally oriented, professionally based, professionally identifying and reflective and developmental stages. Formation of professional communication competence through the latest digital technologies, as a leading technology, is a didactically valuable educational process, reflecting the developed criterion-based indicators in conjunction with the developed typology of exercises, aimed at the final educational product - the subject of professional communication. The developed didactic materials, as applied products, can be applied in the educational process of a language university.

Theoretical significance and didactic value of digital technologies

These digital technologies, reflecting the procedural aspect of foreign language education, are a mechanism for the formation of professional communicative competence, the final educational product of which is determined by the subject of professional communication. Among the many technologies that allow you to create multimedia presentations, in particular CorelDraw, Unled and others, Prezi and Power Point are the most popular. The most widely considered technology service is Prezi and its implementation in the process of foreign language education within the framework of the work of M.M. Magomedova (Magomedova, 2015: 136) [5]. The author also outlines the advantages of the Prezi service over the Power Point program. Prezi is the most famous Power Point alternative. Prezi, a digital cloud presentation, was created in 2009 and immediately exploded as it moved away from “linear” presentations. Prezi.com is a web service that makes it possible to create interactive multimedia presentations with a non-linear structure. In the service for creating multimedia presentations Prezi, there are many opportunities for visualizing presentations using video materials, graphics and other modern technologies. Prezi’s multimedia presentation technology is based on zoom technology. In turn, if “classic” technologies such as Power Point or OpenOffice Impress break a presentation into

slides, then Prezi effects are not associated with switching one slide to another, but with enlarging individual parts of the same slide.

Based on the provisions of M.M. Magomedova offers a comparison of the Prezi and Power Point programs (Magomedova, 2014: 118) [5, 6]. Based on the comparative analysis, we can say that, of course, the Prezi program looks much more advantageous than the Power Point program. However, each program has its own disadvantages and advantages; each person, in a separate particular case, must independently decide what he needs, because each program at first glance presents such similar, and, in turn, such different possibilities for creating multimedia presentations.

DISCUSSION

The experiment was carried out as part of classes in the subject “Language for Special Purposes”. The purpose of this experiment was to test the hypothesis put forward, according to which it was assumed that the success of the formation of professional communicative competence can be ensured through the use of a method of stage-by-stage design of professional communicative activities of students through digital technologies. The respondents were 294 students: in the experimental group - 146 students and in the control group - 148 students. Data from experimental work using the methodology we developed for the stage-by-stage process of developing professional and communicative competence of a foreign language teacher confirm the research hypothesis. All indicators recorded positive dynamics in the formation of professional and communicative competence. The positive dynamics are explained by the use in the experimental group technology for the stage-by-stage formation of professional and communicative competence in the conditions of digitalization.

CONCLUSION

The method of a stage-by-stage process of developing professional communicative competence, based on the use of digital technologies, provides a didactic effect in the formation of professionally significant skills of a future foreign language teacher, ready and capable of intercultural professional communication. The results of the experimental work of our study confirm the correctness of the proposed research hypothesis. The developed methodology for stage-by-stage modeling of the process of formation of professional communicative competence ensures that the desired product is formed according to all indicators of the formation of professional communicative competence in the subject of the PCC, and positive dynamics are observed.

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